

How Scientific Establishments Respond to the Responsible Research Assessment Movement: The Case of the European Research Council (ERC)

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Abstract

How are scientific establishments influenced by reform movements in science policy? In particular, how does an establishment body associated with traditional notions of *research excellence* respond when established orthodoxies are challenged?

This paper presents a case study of how the European Research Council (ERC) has responded to the European Commission-led *responsible research assessment* reform, which advocates for more holistic evaluation recognizing diverse research contributions beyond traditional notions of research excellence.

Through a discourse analysis of publicly available documents, this paper makes three contributions: empirically, it identifies a framing shift at the ERC; analytically, it demonstrates how the ERC navigates complex institutional demands prompted by a reform movement to both maintain its own position and (partially) legitimize the reform agenda; lastly, it advances the literature on research assessment reform.

Keywords: Responsible Research Assessment Reform, CoARA, ERC, Scientific Establishments, Research Policy

1. Introduction

In February 2023, the European Research Council (ERC) signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), a European Commission (EC) led reform initiative aiming to ‘recognise the diverse outputs, practices and activities’, in all the forms in which research, researchers and research institutions are assessed, with the overarching goal of ‘maximising the quality and the impact of research’ (Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment 2022). The ERC’s decision to sign the ARRA signals a noteworthy moment: Europe’s most prestigious funding body, long positioned as a guardian of ‘excellence’ in ‘frontier research’, whose authority rests on defining and enforcing standards of ‘excellence’ and which has shaped notions of research excellence across Europe (Wedlin and Hedmo 2015), is aligning itself with a movement that explicitly challenges the evaluative logics underpinning its established authority: excellence as a sole criteria, competition, selectivity and elite recognition. The ERC thus appears to be confronting the kind of tension long known to face organizations in complex policy environments: negotiating pressures for reform while safeguarding their authority and institutional legitimacy (DiMaggio and Powell 1983; Suchman 1995).

The ERC is a particularly interesting case in the wider discourse on research assessment reform, as it is highly regarded among scientific elites and the broader scientific community (Ulnicane 2023) and itself represents the elite scientific establishment with prominent researchers in its governance structure¹ and peer-review panels². Furthermore, the ERC, according to Hoenig (2018: 12), has contributed to the formation and reproduction of new transnational scientific elites. Coming out of earlier sociology of science studies on elites, Elias (1982: 40) defined scientific establishments as ‘groups of people who collectively are able to exercise a monopolistic control over resources needed by others’ (see also Hoenig 2017: 169). In several ways, the ERC meets this definition: most importantly, it stands as Europe’s largest and most prestigious funding body for fundamental research, with a mandate within the European Commission’s portfolio of funding instruments to concentrate funds for this purpose. Besides, the ERC distributes both material and symbolic resources that are highly valued by scientists (Edler et al. 2014). It provides material resources through large, long-term funding that offer a level of stability rarely available in many national systems

¹ <https://erc.europa.eu/about-erc/erc-president-scientific-council>

² <https://erc.europa.eu/apply-grant/panel-members>

(Laudel and Gläser 2014), as well as the opportunity for researchers to pursue their own interests and topics. Beyond material resources, the ERC distributes symbolic capital: securing an ERC grant confers reputation and prestige, shaping both the careers and job security of individual researchers while enhancing the prestige of their host institutions (Cruz-Castro, Benitez-Amado, and Sanz-Menéndez 2016; Edler et al. 2014). Furthermore, as Edler et al. (2014) observe, the ERC exerts normative influence by shaping the definition of excellent research and affecting the role and autonomy of young grantees. Thus, the material, symbolic, and normative values provided by the ERC make it a highly influential body within the European Research Area (ERA). In the face of declining national research budgets, this influence seems only likely to increase.

Due to the ERC's unique visibility, authority and prestige, it provides a particularly interesting case to explore how scientific establishments navigate pressures and emerging expectations for reform. This paper therefore examines the following questions:

- How has the European Research Council accommodated pressures to reform research assessment, which challenge certain ideas of 'research excellence'?
- Has the ERC substantially reworked the justificatory practices through which it defends its elite status and autonomy within European funding?
- What can this case teach us about the prospects of contemporary reform movements challenging scientific establishments?

The paper is structured as follows: the first section provides context for understanding the ERC's engagement with the ARRA reform agenda, initially by outlining the ERC's historical role and legacy, and then by situating the ERC within the emerging responsible research assessment (RRA)³ reform agenda. Here we further introduce tensions between the ERC's established excellence paradigm and the new RRA principles, which are important context for our empirical focus on how the ERC navigates these pressures while maintaining legitimacy. After setting out the methods and data sources, our empirical account of the ERC's public response to the ARRA agenda is presented, followed by discussion and conclusions of the study's main findings and implications.

³ Throughout this paper, the terms - *RRA*, *ARRA*, and *the CoARA Agreement* - are used interchangeably and carry the same meaning.

1.1 Background: European Research Council and Responsible Research Assessment Reform

The ERC was established in 2007 under the Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (FP7) as a new European-level policy instrument, marking a significant departure from the established objectives and funding practices that had long shaped EU research policy⁴.

Although the origins of the EU research policy date back to the 1950s, policy coordination remained largely intergovernmental until the 1980s (Chou and Gornitzka 2014). Nedeva and Stampfer (2012) and Wedlin and Nedeva (2015) describe this period (1950s - 2000s) as '*Science in Europe*' phase, characterized by fragmented national research systems. From the early 2000s, they identify a transition to '*European Science*', driven by supranational policy efforts of the EU to harmonize and integrate national research systems (Nedeva and Stampfer 2012; Wedlin and Nedeva 2015). A pivotal development during this phase was the launch of the European Research Area (ERA)⁵ in 2000, which according to Wedlin and Nedeva 'marked an increasing level of commensurability between the European research space and national research spaces' (2015: 13). Within this evolving policy landscape, the ERC was created in 2007, representing a break with the previous EU research policy narrative, as a policy instrument specifically designed to support investigator-driven 'frontier research' and strengthen scientific excellence in Europe (Gronbaek 2003). Its establishment was closely linked to the broader objectives of the ERA and the ambition of the Lisbon Strategy 'to become the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world' (European Council 2000). Suggested by an expert group, the term '*frontier*' helped provide justification for the EC's involvement in fundamental research. At the same time, Flink and Peter note that '*frontier*' and '*excellence*' both terms were borrowed from U.S. science policy, '*ironically to compete geopolitically*' (2018: 440). For Mitzner, frontier research falls 'somewhere in between basic and applied research, aligned well with the EU's traditional mission of fostering European competitiveness and the geopolitical objective of the Lisbon

⁴ A key rationale for European-level research policy has been to address challenges common to all member states. This focus is also reflected in the selection criteria for the Framework Programmes (FPs), known as the 'Riesenhuber criteria', which emphasize collaboration and cohesion objectives (Guzzetti 1995).

⁵ After nearly 25 years since the launch of the ERA, it remains a work in progress, with limited success (Cino Pagliarello 2022; European Commission 2025). Research assessment practices have been identified as a key obstacle to achieving ERA objectives and long-term goals - while research assessment reform was initially associated with open science objectives (European Commission 2020) recent policy documents also link it to other ERA structural policies, such as research careers and mobility (European Commission 2025).

Strategy to make Europe the world's leading commercial power, drawing its strength from knowledge' (2020: 269).

'An unusual Brussels creation' (Kelly and Hudson 2022), the ERC marked a significant turning point in EU research policy, signaling a shift from promoting European integration toward European-level competition, fostering scientific excellence and bottom-up fundamental research (Hoenig 2017, 2018; Luukkonen 2014; Ulnicane 2017, 2023). This shift also reoriented EU research funding practices: resources were redirected from organizations to individual researchers (Luukkonen 2014), with grants awarded solely on the basis of scientific excellence and competition. In doing so, the EC departed from its long-standing *juste retour* funding principle - under which member states were expected to receive a 'fair return' roughly proportional to their financial contributions - which had previously structured EU science policy (Luukkonen 2014). Instead, this new funding instrument enacts the principle of *selectivity*, in which 'the best' individuals, organizations, or projects receive more. In the case of the ERC, funding is distributed according to what Young (2015) calls 'zero-sum excellence', funding 'the best of the best' without geographic quotas, with legitimacy resting entirely on the ability of peer-review evaluation to meritocratically identify the most excellent frontier research (Hoenig 2017).

The ERC serves as an intermediary organization (Braun and Guston 2003), mediating between the EC and the scientific community. Currently, the ERC is overseen by the Scientific Council, whose members are eminent researchers⁶ appointed by the EC based on recommendations from an independent Identification Committee (ERC website 2025). The Council operates with considerable autonomy, defining the ERC's scientific strategy, designing funding calls and eligibility criteria, establishing selection and evaluation procedures, appointing peer-review panels, overseeing communication and outreach, and monitoring operations and impact (ERC website 2025). As noted by König, 'no other council, committee, or advisory board in the realm of the European Commission had ever been granted such extensive rights' (2017: 17). This operational autonomy, together with peer-review evaluation, was explicitly suggested by an ERC Expert Group (ERCEG) as essential for the ERC to gain legitimacy and credibility within the scientific community:

The ERC must be granted full operational autonomy in all scientific and scholarly matters including funding policies and decisions. This is necessary to ensure the high

⁶ See <https://erc.europa.eu/about-erc/erc-president-scientific-council>

quality of the work and for maintaining the ERC's credibility in the research community. The community should be fully engaged in the work, including its delivery system, and should provide expert advice, e.g. through international peer review... It is both advantageous and necessary to exploit the capacity for self-government of the research community. This will be essential if the ERC is to obtain trust and credibility within the research community and with society at large (ERCEG 2003: 5, 23).

The creation of the ERC was also strongly backed by scientific elites (Nedeva 2013; Ulnicane 2023), whose advocacy played a crucial role in shaping the Council's authority, legitimacy and positioning (Ulnicane 2023). In the less than two decades since its inaugural funding call, the ERC has gained substantial recognition, status, authority and legitimacy among the scientific community (Luukkonen 2014), establishing itself as a 'European benchmark for scientific prestige' (Kropp 2019), and becoming a status-creating intermediary within European science (Edlund 2020). The ERC has become something of a standard setter for many national research funding bodies and research performing institutions across Europe, influencing norms, practices and organizational decisions made by others (Chou and Gornitzka 2014; Cruz-Castro, Benitez-Amado, and Sanz-Menéndez 2016; Edler et al. 2014; Hoenig 2017; Jong, Franssen, and Pinfield 2021; König 2017; Nedeva et al. 2012; Nedeva 2013; Scholten et al. 2021; Wedlin and Nedeva 2015). Thus, the ERC has played a pivotal role in furthering scientific excellence as a major policy frame in EU science policy (Ulnicane 2023).

Policy frames, however, are neither fixed nor permanent. As Biegelbauer and Weber (2018) argue, such frames are context-dependent and their influence can decline as circumstances change. The emergence of the Responsible Research and Assessment (RRA) agenda has introduced new expectations that go beyond traditional framings of scientific excellence. Since the early 2010s, transnational movements advocating RRA reform have emerged across the global research community, aiming to challenge prevailing research assessment practices, raise awareness of dysfunctions and 'wicked problems' in the research system, and promote new standards and guiding principles to improve research culture and strengthen the organization of the research system (Rushforth and Hammarfelt 2023). These movements have also gained significant momentum within EU research policy. Since 2018, the EC has encouraged member states to revise their research assessment policies (European Commission 2018). In 2021, the EC released a scoping report proposing a coalition-based

approach to reform (European Commission 2021), which led to the establishment of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and the ARRA agreement, published in July 2022⁷.

As Kaltenbrunner (2017) observes, European research policymakers operate on the assumption that the EU's scientific and economic competitiveness can be enhanced by transforming the EU research landscape into a more integrated and homogeneous system. As he explains, 'the EC assumes that when left to their own devices, academic institutions as well as individual communities of researchers naturally lean towards organisational formats that hinder the flow of knowledge across geographical, thematic, and sectoral boundaries' (2017: 284). This belief in the need for supranational coordination underpins not only the EU infrastructure policy but also current efforts to reform research assessment. The EU research policy documents identify current assessment practices among major obstacles to achieving the broader objectives of the ERA and policy goals related to open science, researchers careers, and mobility (European Commission 2020, 2025). The EC scoping report *towards a reform of the research assessment system* reflects these concerns, highlighting 'fragmentation' and 'uneven progress' across institutions and countries as key reasons why supranational coordination is necessary (2021: 5).

1.2 Research Excellence and Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

Excellence refers to a mode of organizing research where academic communities are granted the freedom to organize their social, intellectual, and research activities based solely on the competitive dynamics that emerge among researchers. This model carries the normative assumption that such self-organization, along with any concentration of epistemic and material resources it produces, is inherently superior to arrangements that involve policy makers or other external stakeholders in research governance. Genealogically, this resonates with Polanyi's (1962) programmatic, and much criticized, view of the scientific system as a self-organizing 'republic', in which researchers collectively advance knowledge according to shared internal norms, rather than external political control or oversight. For sociological critics, these 'common sense' arguments are mobilized mostly strategically by academic

⁷ Building upon earlier key global initiatives, such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), the Leiden Manifesto and the Hong Kong Principles, the European discourse on RRA has broadened the scope and focus of prior efforts. Unlike DORA, which emerged from within the scientific community (Cagan 2013), the ARRA reform was initiated and supported by the EC as part of its efforts to reform research assessment practices across the ERA (European Commission 2021).

communities in contests between science and politics, to protect autonomy and resist direct political interference. Against this backdrop, the recent movement for research assessment reform should not be understood as a purely technical effort to improve evaluative procedures. Willingly or not – it gets entangled in enduring tussles between political and scientific visions over how research ought to be organized, particularly concerning questions of autonomy over the distribution of material and symbolic resources.

Although vague and contested, the notion of excellence became central to evaluation practices over recent decades, and commonly invoked in assessments of individual researchers, proposals, and organizations, with its rhetoric deeply embedded across various systems (Jong, Franssen, and Pinfield 2021). Amplified and accelerated by trends such as new public management, the term excellence became commonly associated with a strong output orientation, performance indicators and rankings, competition, selectivity, and elite recognition (Antonowicz et al. 2017; Jong, Franssen, and Pinfield 2021; Moore et al. 2017; Rushforth et al. 2025; Young et al. 2015).

ARRA has an ambiguous relationship with these notions of excellence. Though it does not take an explicit stance against selective funding and ‘research excellence’, several of ARRA’s demands and values appear antagonistic to principles of competition, selectivity and performance indicators synonymous with the excellence regime. ARRA emphasizes collaboration over competition, condemns the use of quantitative performance indicators and benchmarking, and calls for alternative notions of research quality to be considered beyond traditional outputs contributing to specialty knowledge, including education, open science, academic service, and societal engagement.

ARRA also provides specific recommendations for research funders, such as:

- Assessments should consider disciplinary, multi-, inter-, and trans-disciplinary research as well as contributions to knowledge generation and scientific, technological, economic, cultural, and societal impact (p. 8);
- The use of post-peer review lotteries for funding applications (p. 20);
- Piloting alternative/new assessment criteria, tools, and processes (e.g., narrative CV format, competency-based CV format, evidence-based CV format, diversification of research careers and associated career progression (p. 18).

Looking beyond only ARRA, Rushforth et al. (2025) argue that the wider RRA reform agenda seeks to inspire a departure from narrow, output-focused definitions of research excellence, thus constituting a challenge to the professional-disciplinary and excellence- and competition-oriented performance paradigms that have dominated over the last four decades. Indeed, a prominent statement from the RRA movement, the *Harnessing the Metric Tide* report, explicitly calls the term excellence ‘problematic’ and states the need to replace ‘the contested and ill-defined term 'excellence' with an alternative that reflects plural dimensions of research quality and impact, and encompasses processes, cultures and behaviours’ (Curry, Gadd, and Wilsdon 2022: 31).

As Rushforth et al. (2025) note, challenges to excellence-based performance paradigms are much more likely to generate a layering effect among research performance paradigms, rather than a straightforward replacement of excellence by the RRA. More established and mature paradigms, such as the disciplinary and excellence paradigms, are deeply institutionalized and have accrued legitimacy over decades. By contrast, the RRA paradigm is newly emerging, still in the process of gaining support, and therefore vulnerable to cherry-picking, symbolic compliance, and resistance⁸.

The challenge of the RRA agenda to the excellence paradigm has placed sufficient pressure on the ERC to review its processes and publicly explain and justify its position. As a key symbolic torchbearer for the research excellence paradigm and an important standard setter for European research funding, the ERC provides an especially interesting and important case for studying how an institution navigates the tensions between the emerging RRA and the established excellence paradigm on which its legitimacy is rooted. In the following sections, we examine how the ERC has engaged with the RRA agenda, responded to concerns, justified its position, and navigated the frictions between these two performance paradigms.

2. Conceptual framework

To analyze how ERC has responded to reform, this study draws on Gieryn’s concept of boundary work (1999). Boundary work refers to the strategic practices through which scientists and scientific institutions define, defend, or negotiate the limits of ‘real’ science,

⁸ While the ARRA received support across Europe, it was not universally welcomed. For instance, when the ERC announced its intention to sign the CoARA agreement, representatives of the German Rectors’ Conference expressed concerns that the decision could undermine the ERC’s longstanding focus on excellence, see <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/german-universities-still-wary-eu-push-reform-research-assessment>

thereby demarcating credible knowledge, legitimate scientific methods and professional authority. Through drawing, maintaining, redrawing, or selectively blurring domain boundaries, actors seek to protect autonomy, maintain legitimacy, and secure both material (e.g., funding) and symbolic (e.g., prestige) resources (Gieryn 1983). As Gieryn notes, such boundary construction serves the pursuit of professional goals, including ‘acquisition of intellectual authority and career opportunities... and protection of the autonomy of scientific research from political interference’ (1983: 781).

Boundary work is both discursive and practical, as scientists attempt to draw ‘*rhetorical boundary between science and some less authoritative, residual non-science*’ (Gieryn 1999: 4-5), translating these distinctions into strategic action that enables them to establish epistemic authority (Gieryn 1999: 23). Gieryn identified three primary genres of boundary work (1999): Boundary Expansion – the extension of authority or expertise into domains already claimed by other professions or occupations; Boundary Expulsion – the exclusion of outsiders, described as ‘*expulsion of deviant scientists, as a means of social control and of preserving professional reputation and public confidence*’ (Gieryn 1995: 294); and Protection of Autonomy – safeguarding professional control over activities, resources, and privileges from external pressures.

While Gieryn’s framework provides a valuable starting point, we adapted and expanded these genres iteratively (see ‘Data collection and Analysis’ below) to capture how the ERC’s responds to the RRA reform agenda. Specifically, we identify three forms of boundary work: *Boundary Absorption*, *Boundary Preservation* and *Protection of Autonomy*. Each type represents a distinct mechanism through which epistemic authority and legitimacy are challenged, maintained, or recalibrated by the ERC.

In this context, we divided *boundary absorption* into two categories: incorporation of ARRA principles and post-hoc alignment. The former refers to the integration of ARRA principles and recommendations by the ERC into its assessment criteria, processes and practices, while the latter involves not the adoption of new elements to comply with the ARRA, but rather rhetorical tactics demonstrating how existing practices were already aligned with ARRA. Through absorption, the ERC recalibrates its practices around selected ARRA elements, thereby maintaining its own legitimacy while simultaneously lending legitimacy to those elements. *Boundary preservation*, in contrast, refers to the exclusion or disregard of reform elements or recommendations that could be perceived as potential threats to the ERC’s

authority. *Protection of autonomy* captures elements that are non-negotiable to the ERC: unlike absorption or preservation, which involve varying degrees of engagement with reform elements, autonomy protection boundary tactics establish rigid boundaries that are non-negotiable. These ideal type categories help to identify and make sense of differing tactics employed at specific moments and together help to analyze how an establishment body responds publicly to a reform movement that unsettles legitimacy discourses through which it has established, protected and expanded its authority in European science policy.

3. Data Collection and Analysis

The study employs discourse analysis of publicly available documents, including speeches, announcements, and statements by the ERC, as well as related media coverage, reports, and key policy and procedural documents such as work programmes, annual reports, reviewer guidelines, information for applicants, and Scientific Council plenary meeting minutes spanning from 2021 to 2025. Document selection prioritized materials preceding major debates on research assessment reform, particularly those marking the initiatives' announcement, reception, and subsequent development. Documents were selected using purposive sampling – only materials directly relevant to the ERC's engagement with the RRA reform were included. This diverse corpus captures both the ERC's internal discussions and its external communications, reflecting the ERC's strategic positioning over time. Annex 1 provides the list of documents analyzed, including the date, type, author/title, and source.

Once assembled, all texts were imported into Atlas.ti for analysis. The analytical process followed a constant comparative approach, moving back and forth between data and Gieryn's (1995, 1999) boundary work framework. In this study, both inductive and deductive coding were employed. Coding was refined over successive rounds, supported by memo writing to track emerging patterns, themes, and arguments across the corpus. As coding developed, we noticed that Gieryn's original triad of boundary work concepts (Boundary Expansion, Boundary Expulsion, and Protection of Autonomy) did not fit the data wholly adequately, leading us to further rounds of discussion and returning to the data. Through iterative back and forth, we eventually settled upon three modes of boundary work, introduced in the previous section: boundary absorption, boundary preservation and protection of autonomy. This adapted framework was subsequently applied deductively across the whole dataset.

The findings are presented through a composite narrative, that is largely chronological, organized around a timeline of key events and ERC responses. Tracing developments

sequentially allows for a dynamic and complex picture of the ERC's response to the RRA agenda to be built up, capturing not only *what* kinds of boundary work were employed by the ERC but also *when* and in response to *which* pressures.

Our findings are divided into three chronological sub-sections. The first section outlines early signals of reform engagement and strategic positioning by the ERC during 2021-2022, prior to signing the ARRA agreement. The second section addresses the turning point when the ERC decided to sign the agreement, examining how it justified its position and addressed emerging concerns. The third section focuses on the institutionalization of changes in ERC procedures. Throughout, selected quotes from the analyzed documents are used to illustrate how the ERC deployed the boundary work tactics to navigate the tensions between the established research excellence performance paradigm and the emerging RRA agenda.

4. Findings

4.1 Early Signals of Reform Engagement (2021-2022)

As previously mentioned, in November 2021 the EC published the scoping report '*Towards a Reform of the Research Assessment System*', which synthesized the outcome of a consultation conducted between March and November 2021 by the EC Directorate for Research and Innovation, Open Science Unit, with European stakeholders. The exercise aimed to identify challenges in existing research assessment approaches across the ERA and to explore ways to facilitate and accelerate change. The report proposed a coalition approach based on agreed principles and actions, to be endorsed by individual organizations, noting that 'such a coalition would help ensure ownership of the initiative by the signatories' (2021: 8). Notably, the ERC was not among the European stakeholders consulted (see Annex 1 of the scoping report).

Nevertheless, it is important to note that in July 2021 the ERC took some initial steps to this wider reform agenda by officially signing the DORA declaration (ERC plans for 2022 announced, ERC website). Similar to the ARRA, one of DORA's main recommendations is to avoid using journal-based metrics, such as Journal Impact Factors, in the evaluation process - a principle shared by both initiatives. In doing so, the ERC sought to distance themselves from and further delegitimize the use of 'inappropriate metrics' in its evaluations. This *boundary absorption* – specifically, *post-hoc alignment* with DORA - in official communications was framed as 'in line with its long-standing adherence to the highest

standards of research assessment’ (ERC plans for 2022 announced, ERC website). The ERC also provided further post-hoc alignment of their peer-review procedures with broad principles of responsible assessment in their 2021 annual report:

Since its inception, the ERC’s peer-review evaluation process has been carefully designed to identify scientific excellence irrespective of the gender, age, nationality or institution of the Principal Investigator and other criteria that could potentially introduce bias, and to take career breaks, as well as unconventional research career paths, into account. The evaluations are monitored to guarantee transparency, fairness and impartiality in the treatment of proposals. (Annual report 2021: 36)

As noted in the ERC’s Annual Report 2022, at its Scientific Council plenary meeting in December 2021 - within a month after the release of the EC scoping report - the Council agreed that ‘it needed to develop its own position on reforming research assessment and decided to set up a Task Force on this issue’ (2022: 43).

It took some time before the ERC decided to sign the agreement in December 2022. Earlier that year, an interview was given in Science Business by the ERC’s president Maria Leptin (whose appointment in November 2021 coincided with the EC’s active efforts to build a coalition and advance the reform agenda following the scoping report) noted that the Council was going to set up a task force on research assessment to improve its own evaluation process and give examples to other funders, stating - ‘we hope to lead in implementing the reforms that emerge from this consultation with the community’. In the interim, in June 2022, the Council hosted an expert workshop aimed ‘to reflect on current ERC assessment principles and practices, and to provide input to the ERC Scientific Council’ (Annual Report 2022: 36). The ARRA was officially launched in July 2022, signed by more than 350 organizations at the initial stage; however, the ERC was not among the early adopters.

In September 2022, Maria Leptin addressed the topic of research assessment in her speech ‘Research Excellence – Quo Vadis?’ at the Nordic University Days with Nordic rectors, through boundary absorption tactics, lending legitimacy to the reform movement and framing the ARRA not as a threat to excellence but as a ‘well-balanced’ approach that does not attempt to lower the quality of research:

If you look at certain recent trends, it is possible then it is possible to conclude that the concept of excellence in research is being called into question... Some would even argue that the recently published ‘Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment’ is

partly an attempt to move away from the idea of excellence in research.... Do we need to change criteria related to scientific excellence? I do not believe this to be the case. If you look at the Agreement it is rather well balanced... So the reformers are not attempting to lower the quality of research. Rather the intention seems to be the opposite... What they are questioning is taking short cuts for judging excellence, for example, by considering Journal Impact Factors or H-Indices rather than a researcher's contribution to knowledge or their grant proposal. (Leptin's speech, Research Excellence – Quo Vadis? 2022)

This suggests an attempt to justify boundary absorption of the new agenda, without casting doubts on the probity of their existing processes. In the same speech, Leptin performed post-hoc alignment by rejecting the use of journal-based metrics for judging excellence and stating that the organization 'is thus clearly committed to basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central'. Indeed, to defend their process as air-tight, in an interview with Science Business (2022) discussing the ERC's 'success formula' of grantees winning Nobel Prizes, Leptin made the case that the ERC's 'success begins with the evaluation process', that its peer-review system is 'strict' and a 'brutally critical assessment', leaning into myths of peer review premised upon a) organized skepticism b) rational design and c) intense competition of the ERC instrument ensuring meritocracy, without acknowledging any challenges or limitations associated with peer-review evaluation.

In a *protection of autonomy* boundary work move, the ERC president made clear that scientific excellence as the sole criterion for ERC funding remains untouchable, setting out a boundary marker for what is non-negotiable for the ERC:

What is not in question are the basic principles of the ERC. The sole criterion of scientific excellence is here to stay at the ERC!.. This approach is critical to the success of the ERC and we have no intention of changing it. (Leptin's speech, Research Excellence – Quo Vadis? 2022)

Despite performing defensive boundary work tactics like post-hoc alignment and protection of autonomy, Leptin was clearly still committing the ERC to change, as regarding the signing of the agreement, Leptin stated: 'This is a very important topic with wide implications and we want to take our time and get this right'. This speech thus served as a boundary-drawing intervention: signaling to policymakers that the ERC aligns with broader EU priorities and is responsive to reform pressures, while simultaneously drawing a clear line around what is

non-negotiable for the ERC. At the same time, Leptin further legitimized the reform movement in her November 2022 speech to the European Parliament's Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE) by acknowledging that 'many of the demands being made in regard to research assessment, particularly those from the younger generation, are legitimate'.

4.2 Turning Point: Signing the Agreement

In December 2022, during its 88th plenary meeting, the ERC Scientific Council decided to sign the ARRA but without joining the coalition⁹. The ERC subsequently announced that it would sign the agreement on 19 December 2022. Three days later, the ERC's President published an editorial in the Coimbra Group newsletter 'Reaffirming the ERC's Commitment to Scientific Excellence', communicating its decision to influential academic institutions. In the editorial, Leptin reaffirmed that scientific excellence remains the sole criterion for ERC funding, but accepted some forms of boundary absorption in response to ARRA, such as the introduction of narrative CVs, allowing applicants to explain career breaks or unconventional career paths, explicitly weighting the project proposal more than the PI, and recognizing 'exceptional contributions' to the research community. By 'exceptional', Leptin clarified that they refer to contributions that go beyond regular duties, such as 'acting as peer reviewer for journals or supervising their own students', even though these activities were recommended for inclusion by the ARRA (2022: 4) and in practice, ERC grantees recruit and supervise PhD students and postdocs as part of their research teams.

The ERC's decision to sign the agreement was not universally welcomed. In January 2023, a representative of the German Rectors' Conference told Science Business that the decision could undermine the ERC's longstanding focus on excellence. However, the ERC Executive Agency reported to the ERC Scientific Council in February 2023 that ERC's statement on research assessment and planned changes were 'well received by the community. Good media interviews and positive social media feedback had been recorded' (89th plenary meeting minutes: 3-4). As Science Business notes, the ERC's decision was also welcomed by representatives of ALLEA, Science Europe, and the Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities (2023).

⁹ As stated, '*The Scientific Council is an independent body, and it should remain as such, therefore it should abstain from joining any coalitions*' ([88th plenary meeting minutes](#), p.3)

Amid these discussions, ERC moved forward by officially signing the agreement in February 2023. Although signatories are required to submit their action plans outlining the changes they aim to implement within a year of signing, the ERC's action plan is still pending, according to the CoARA website. Nevertheless, the ERC has introduced changes in its work programmes and published a dedicated report - *Evaluation of Research Proposals: the Why and What of the ERC's Recent Changes*. In the next section, we will discuss these changes in detail.

4.3 Institutionalization of Changes

Following the ERC's formal endorsement of the ARRA in February 2023, the Council moved from rhetorical movements to implementation of changes. The 2024 Work Programme, published in July 2023, introduced some updates and provided justifications for the proposed changes in response to the ARRA. Notable updates, aligning to *boundary absorption* tactics, included:

- Introduction of Narrative CVs - allowing applicants to justify the significance of their contributions, describing career breaks and diverse career paths. Applicants are also allowed to list up to ten diverse research outputs and provide additional information on 'exceptional contributions' to the scientific community, even though the latter are not evaluated separately. As Leptin framed these adjustments 'This is a further turn-away from quantitative assessment towards content' (Changes in the Evaluation of Proposals for ERC Grants 2023).
- More weight on proposal: according to the ERC report *Evaluation of Research Proposals: the Why and What of the ERC's Recent Changes*, more weight is now formally placed on the research proposal rather than the PI. Only proposals are scored and ranked on a 1-5 scale, while applicants receive an overall qualitative assessment. In contrast to the introduction of Narrative CVs - which represents the boundary absorption incorporation of new RRA elements - Leptin framed this change as a post-hoc alignment: 'We also established formally a principle that has already been used in practice, namely that the major weight of the evaluation is put on the project proposal' (Changes in the evaluation of proposals for ERC grants 2023) however, no fixed weight is assigned between project and PI evaluation (ERC – Guide for peer reviewers, Starting and Consolidator Grant 2024; ERC – Guide for peer reviewers, Advanced Grant 2025).

- Terminology change: the ERC decided to eliminate the term ‘high-risk, high-gain’, seen as potentially confusing and problematic’, which according to them ‘often invoked to discourage evaluation panels from conservatism in their choice of what to fund’ (Evaluation of Research Proposals: the Why and What of the ERC's Recent Changes 2024: 5).

In terms of *boundary preservation*, the ERC rejected two of the three recommendations made by ARRA to research funders. It retained selectivity and peer-review based funding rather than adopting ‘post-peer review lotteries’ for allocating grants, though the ERC noted in its report that discussions about partial randomization and other innovative funding approaches would continue in the future (Evaluation of Research Proposals: the Why and What of the ERC's Recent Changes report 2024: 12). Regarding the recognition of supervision and mentorship (another recommendation for inclusion by the ARRA), the ERC explained that while applicants had previously been asked to list the number of PhDs and postdocs they had supervised, this requirement was removed: ‘we were unable to come up with any other reliable and fair measure for ‘good mentorship’ and thus concluded that this information should no longer be asked for’ (see Evaluation of Research Proposals: the Why and What of the ERC's Recent Changes report 2024: 7).

Regarding *boundary protection*, scientific excellence continues to function as a central boundary marker for the ERC. Even the changes that were introduced were framed as a ‘reaffirmation’ of excellence (Reaffirming the ERC’s Commitment to Scientific Excellence, Coimbra Group newsletter 2023). This criterion is treated as non-negotiable, and the ERC resists the inclusion of additional dimensions, such as economic or societal impact, in its evaluation framework, invoking its legal mandate and mission to justify its position:

The ERC as a funder of frontier research should retain the sole criterion of scientific excellence, as legally enshrined in the acts establishing the EU research and innovation framework programme, and not move towards evaluating economic or societal impact. Using economic or societal impact as explicit evaluation criteria would disfavour fundamental, curiosity-driven research that may not have an immediate or obvious economic or societal impact but is nevertheless important for scientific progress. (ERC report, Evaluation of Research Proposals: the Why and What of the ERC's Recent Changes 2024: 4)

Finally, after signing the agreement and announcing the changes in July 2023, Leptin, in her November 2023 speech ‘A Critical and Prospective Stance on Excellence and Open Science’ at the Coimbra Group High-Level Seminar on Research Policy, described the term ‘excellence’ as ‘polarizing’ and emphasized the need to distinguish between the ‘principle of excellence’, which according to her refers to the distribution of resources at the EU level, and the definition of ‘excellence’. Leptin further criticized the ‘juste retour’ funding principle as ‘inefficient’, defending selectivity and competition, and also noted that the principle of excellence is not intended to allocate funding in a way that favors elites or leads to the concentration of resources:

To some people, ‘excellence’ has come to mean a deliberate policy of concentrating research funding on an elite group of institutions or individuals, using narrow metrics and creating a closed shop or ‘Matthew Effect’ where ‘the rich get richer...The ‘principle of excellence’ by itself does not imply concentrating funding on an elite group of institutions or individuals using narrow metrics. And I think it would be very regrettable if the EU Framework Programmes departed from the ‘principle of excellence’. (Leptin’s speech, A Critical and Prospective Stance on Excellence and Open Science 2023)

Leptin’s intervention reflects the broader tensions between EU political and scientific ideas of research organization, particularly regarding the distribution of resources. Historically, EU science policy has focused on integration and cohesion, aiming to balance participation across member states. In contrast, selectivity and merit-based evaluation are standard for scientific community, which are at odds with some EU political goals and may lead to the concentration of resources in already strong institutions and regions (Hoenig 2017).

Leptin further stated that ‘the public discussion on assessing researchers has mixed these ‘orthogonal’ categories’ - referring to evaluations in different contexts and for different types of activities. As an example, she explained that the ERC defines what counts as excellence by specifying the characteristics and qualities it considers important in their context but leaves the actual operationalization of excellence to review panels.

The rhetorical tactics and changes discussed in this section illustrate how the ERC has responded to the RRA movement through a combination of boundary absorption, preservation, and protection. By adopting limited RRA-aligned practices while reaffirming scientific excellence as its sole criterion, the ERC seeks to maintain its authority and

legitimacy, demonstrating the delicate balancing act of a prestigious scientific establishment responding to evolving expectations.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The study examined how scientific establishments respond to the responsible research assessment movement, using the ERC as a case study to explore how it has navigated pressures from the EC-led ARRA agenda to reform research assessment, particularly concerning ‘research excellence’.

The study findings reveal a complex layering dynamic in which the ERC negotiates between its longstanding commitment to the established research excellence performance paradigm and its response to the emerging RRA reform agenda. Although influential statements like CoARA’s ARRA do not entirely contradict the ERC’s established norms and practices, some recommendations challenge its procedures and collide with its core value of excellence as the sole criterion for organizing (and legitimating) funding allocation. This tension has disrupted the ERC’s formal procedures and communications, prompting the organization to respond strategically - allocating resources, setting up a task force, and engaging in strategic rhetoric - to navigate a changing environment. To address our research question, we find that the ERC simultaneously legitimizes and resists reform pressures.

As the findings demonstrate, although the ERC has adapted in certain ways, these adaptations are selective: on the one hand, the ERC endorses the reform movement by formally signing the ARRA and absorbing some of its principles – for example, by rejecting the use of metrics in evaluation and introducing narrative CVs; on the other hand, these changes are not fundamentally transformative: the ERC’s identity remains largely anchored in the scientific excellence performance paradigm, as it simultaneously redraws boundaries and uses excellence-related arguments to protect its authority and legitimacy in resource distribution. Through such boundary work strategies, the ERC aligns formally with reform imperatives while simultaneously defending its core principles - scientific excellence as the sole criterion, competition, selectivity, and peer-review evaluation.

These dynamics lead directly to our second research question: has the ERC substantially reworked the justificatory practices through which it defends its elite status and autonomy within European funding? The ERC has selectively reworked its justificatory practices in response to the ARRA reform agenda, but these changes are incremental rather than

transformative. As Jong, Franssen, and Pinfield (2025) argue, the research system is unlikely to undergo significant reform as long as the assumptions underpinning competition and meritocratic ideals remain unchallenged. They further note that research funders, operating within the excellence regime and constrained by government policy and scientific elites, cannot simply abandon the concept of excellence. Instead, they typically employ mitigation strategies - patching, pluralizing, or transforming their activities - to reconfigure excellence. Of these, transformation strategies have the potential to challenge the assumptions behind merit-based competition; yet, as the authors caution, such strategies 'are at risk of being dismissed or co-opted by actors and institutions with strong attachments to the excellence regime' (2025: 16). In the case of the ERC, its response to the RRA agenda does not follow strategies of patching, pluralizing, or transformation; instead, the ERC actively defends excellence, which, as demonstrated in the findings, has been used to protect its autonomy and maintain its authority.

The ERC, as Edlund (2020) notes, has built its authority by framing its evaluation process as exact, expert-driven, exclusively merit-based - tough enough to respond to Western European critiques that the competition was not too fierce, yet fair enough to counter Eastern European concerns that it was too fierce - while also gaining validation from other actors in the field, such as research funding organizations across Europe. Edlund further suggested that such authority is fragile and dependent on legitimacy among stakeholders: if belief in the ERC's evaluation system wavers, its authority can erode. In this context, the ARRA presents a challenge to the ERC, gaining growing support across Europe and putting pressure on the organization to respond and defend its position.

Furthermore, as Musselin (2013) notes, peer-review evaluations often empower academic elites - those who participate in review panels and control access to both material and symbolic resources - thereby reinforcing hierarchies within the academic community. On this dimension, the ARRA has not challenged, but in some ways reinforced the ERC's valorization of peer review. Existing studies highlight limitations in ERC's peer-evaluation processes, including conservatism and risk aversion (Luukkonen 2012; Van Den Besselaar, Sandström, and Schiffbaenker 2018) and bias against applicants with highly novel profiles (Veugelers, Wang, and Stephan 2025; Wang, Veugelers, and Stephan 2017). Yet the ERC continues to rely on peer review for funding decisions and has rejected post-review lotteries recommended by the ARRA. In addition to reinforcing excellence as the sole funding criterion, peer review embodies the idea of self-organization in science. Partial

randomization, by contrast, challenges this entrenched power structure and self-organization idea (Horbach, Tjldink, and Bouter 2022; Woods and Wilsdon 2021). In the context of our conceptual framework, these responses reflect *boundary preservation*, a means for the ERC to continue to legitimate its monopolistic control over ‘frontier’ research.

The study also explored how EU political and scientific ideas of research organization intersect. Here, tensions are evident between the EU policy logic, exemplified by the ‘juste retour’ principle, and the scientific logic of self-organization. Critics have argued, with regard to the ‘excellence principle’, the ERC’s adherence to it has contributed to a ‘geopolitical oligarchization’ within Europe and elite formation within the ERA in ways that contradict its goals and cultural legitimacy, disproportionately favoring institutions in Northwestern Europe while marginalizing those in Southern and Eastern regions (Hoenig 2017, 2018). As Hoenig (2017) notes, this has reinforced structural inequalities within the European research landscape, leaving peripheral regions underrepresented, with only a few grantees. Notably, issues of concentration and cumulative advantage - commonly referred to as the ‘Matthew Effect’ - are not directly addressed in the ARRA. Nevertheless, with regard to concentration issues, the ERC defends its ‘zero-sum’ excellence funding model by arguing that the *juste retour* principle can be inefficient. Discussions around the allocation of resources reflect a fundamental tension between two logics: the EU policy logic, based on *juste retour*, and the scientific logic of self-organization, as different actors invoke these logics to justify their views on how resources should be distributed and by whom, demonstrating that debates over excellence (and by extension research assessment reform) are not merely about scientific quality, but fundamentally about the distribution of resources.

The case of the ERC further illustrates that contemporary reform movements face significant constraints when challenging scientific establishments. The ERC’s selective adoption of reform principles and the voluntary nature of the agreement demonstrate how establishment bodies can strategically align themselves with reform movements, while cherry-picking some ARRA principles to preserve their authority and legitimacy. Thus, the case also highlights the limitations of voluntary reform initiatives, such as ARRA, in challenging entrenched paradigms, particularly when institutions are responsible for implementation. Recognizing these dynamics is essential for understanding the pathways and constraints of reform in complex policy environments.

Lastly, our conceptual framework, adapted from Gieryn's research on boundary work, proved particularly useful in this analysis, as it allowed us to conceptualize how the ERC actively constructs, blurs, and defends the boundaries of its established norms and practices while navigating complex institutional demands prompted by the reform movement.

Finally, the case study demonstrates that reform adoption within scientific establishments is neither linear nor total; rather, it is strategic, gradual, negotiable, selective, and shaped by the need to safeguard authority and legitimacy. For policymakers and reform activists, this underscores the importance of engaging with scientific establishment bodies strategically, recognizing their central role as both gatekeepers and facilitators of change. It also suggests that collective action by CoARA and other initiatives that rely largely on voluntary action, are capable of placing pressure on scientific establishment bodies to reform, and that this can lead to changes, even if partial and incomplete.

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Conflict of interest

None declared.

Ethics statement

None required because the study is based on publicly available data.

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Annex 1: Documents used in the Analysis

Type of Document	Date	Author / Title	Source
Speech	Sep 2022	ERC President Maria Leptin – <i>Research Excellence, Quo Vadis?</i>	ERC Website
	Nov 2022	ERC President Maria Leptin – <i>Speech to the European Parliament's ITRE Committee</i>	ERC Website
	Nov 2023	ERC President Maria Leptin – <i>A critical and prospective stance on excellence and open science</i>	ERC Website
Public Statements	Dec 2022	ERC – <i>Reaffirming the ERC's commitment to scientific excellence</i>	Coimbra Group Newsletter
	Jan 2024	ERC – <i>ERC Statement on the next EU framework for research and innovation</i>	ERC Website
	Feb 2024	Maria Leptin – <i>Evaluation of research proposals: rationale for recent changes</i>	ERC Website
Announcements	Jul 2021	<i>ERC plans for 2022 announced</i>	ERC Website
	Dec 2022	ERC – <i>ERC Scientific Council decides changes to the evaluation forms and processes for the 2024 calls</i>	ERC Website
	Apr 2023	ERC – <i>Evaluation of ERC grant proposals: what to expect in 2024</i>	ERC Website
	Jul 2023	ERC – <i>Changes in evaluation of ERC grant proposals</i>	ERC Website
	Jun 2025	ERC – <i>Changes to the 2026 and 2027 Work Programmes</i>	ERC Website
Procedural Documents	2024	ERC – <i>Work Programme 2024</i>	ERC Website
	2025	ERC – <i>Work Programme 2025</i>	ERC Website
	2026	ERC – <i>Work Programme 2026</i>	ERC Website
	2022-2023	ERC – <i>Scientific Council Plenary Meeting Minutes (86th–90th meetings; 87th unavailable)</i>	ERC Website
	2025	ERC – <i>Guide for peer reviewers, Advanced Grant 2025</i>	ERC Website
	2024	ERC – <i>Guide for peer reviewers, Starting and Consolidator Grant 2024</i>	ERC Website
	2026	ERC – <i>Information for Applicants, Starting and Consolidator Grant calls 2026</i>	ERC Website
Reports	2021	ERC – <i>Annual Report on ERC activities and achievements 2021</i>	ERC Website

	2022	ERC – <u>Annual Report on ERC activities and achievements 2022</u>	ERC Website
	2023	ERC – <u>Annual Report on ERC activities and achievements 2023</u>	ERC Website
	Mar 2025	UEFISCDI – <u>Best Practices in Research Assessment Reform Across Europe</u>	Zenodo
Media Coverage	Feb 2022	<u>France helps Brussels move ahead with ‘disruptive’ plan for research assessment</u>	Science Business
	Dec 2022	<u>European Research Council announces plan to update its evaluation system</u>	Science Business
	Jan 2023	<u>German universities still wary of EU push to reform research assessment</u>	Science Business
	May 2023	<u>Research lobbies cheer European Research Council rollout of ‘inclusive’ evaluation rules</u>	Science Business
	Feb 2024	<u>The European Research Council has changed how it evaluates applicants. Here’s why</u>	Science Business